

Fig. 1—Effect of substitution of natural rubber (smoked sheet) by reclaim (whole tyre) in high-sulphur compound.

Despite the different modes of studies made in reclaimed rubber⁴, thermal analysis has not been carried out as yet. Keeping this point in consideration the present investigation has been undertaken to study the effect of substitution of natural rubber by reclaimed rubber (otherwise called reclaim) in high sulphur compounds, where the limiting proportion of sulphur (50 parts)^{5,6} has been used. The recipe of such compounds is shown in Table 1, and their DTA thermograms in Figure 1. Curves I and IV represent compounds based solely on natural

TABLE 1—FORMULATION OF COMPOUNDS* (PARTS BY WEIGHT) ANALYSED BY DTA

	I	II	III	IV
Smoked sheet	100.0	75.0	50.0	—
Reclaim	—	50.0	100.0	200.0
Stearic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
BA**	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Sulphur	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0

rubber and reclaim respectively, whereas curves II and III are for compounds based on their blends. In general, three different regions have been noted—the T_m of the curative (here sulphur), curing exothermic region and the degradation region. The characteristic features of each thermogram such as peak area, initiation and peak temperatures, etc. can be noted from the curing exotherms (starting above 160° and ending

** Butyraldehyde aniline.

*The reclaim contains about 50% of rubber hydrocarbon. Therefore, the proportion of reclaim used is twice that of smoked sheet to be substituted.

near 260°) of these curves. Heat evolution is found to diminish on gradual replacement of natural rubber by reclaim, the rate of decrease being slow at first, then becomes much faster and finally becomes slow again. Rate of reaction as observed from the slope of the peak with respect to the base line does not show much of difference in compounds based on natural rubber-reclaim blends, except in compounds based entirely on either of the two rubbers. Initiation temperature is however, practically the same in compounds based on natural rubber or its blend containing a major portion of the former. On the other hand, the temperature of initiation in compounds based on reclaim or its blend with natural rubber containing loss by weight of the latter are almost identical. On comparison between blends, changes in the ratio of natural rubber to reclaim show some change in initiation temperature. Regarding peak temperatures, little differences have been noted in all the above compounds. An exotherm around 350° has been observed in case of the natural rubber based compounds (curve I).

Detailed investigations on the effect of different ingredients in compounds based on reclaim as well as its blends with different polymers are also being carried out in this laboratory. Results will be published later on.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes. Part VIII: 1-Histidinate bis(Biguanide) cobalt(III) and (aminoacidato) bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) Salts.

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HISTIDINE(I) (histH) may bind to a metal ion as a tridentate NNO donor¹⁻⁴ or as bidentate NN donor^{4,5} or bidentate NO donor⁶. Since cobalt(III) is consistently six coordinate in its complexes

the synthesis and elucidation of the structure of the mixed chelate $[\text{Co}(\text{hist})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$ have been undertaken in order to examine which of the above three behaviours takes precedence. Several other mixed chelates $[\text{Co}(\text{AB})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$ containing one bidentate amino acid ($\text{ABH}=\text{dl-}\alpha\text{-alanine}$, $\beta\text{-alanine}$, 1-leucine and $\text{dl-}\text{valine}$), (donor set NO), and two biguanide moieties (donor set NN) also have been synthesised in order to aid in the elucidation of the structure of $[\text{Co}(\text{hist})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$.

Experimental

Biguanide acid sulphate⁷ and cis diammine bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) base⁸ were prepared according to published procedures. The yields of the following compounds were in the range 0.3 to 0.4 g).

l-histidinate bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) bromide : Cis-diammine bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) base (1.3 g) was taken in water (20 ml) and was stirred with *l*-histidine hydrochloride (0.8 g), first at room temperature for 20 min and then on a steam bath for forty minutes. The solution was then filtered, neutralised with 1:3 HCl, concentrated (10 ml) and treated with KBr (~1g) and allowed to stand overnight in the refrigerator. The orange red crystals were collected and recrystallised twice from minimum-volume of hot water.

[Found : N, 30.4 ; Br, 26.6 ; Co, 10.2 ; H₂O, 3.0 per cent ; Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{hist})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 30.6 ; Br, 26.9 ; Co, 9.9 ; H₂O, 3.0 per cent].

l-histidinate bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) iodide : The synthesis was similar to that described above, KI being used instead of KBr.

Found : N, 26.6 ; I, 36.5 ; Co, 8.7 ; H₂O, 2.8 ; per cent ; Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{hist})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 26.5 ; I, 36.9 ; Co, 8.6 ; H₂O 2.6 per cent].

d,l-α-alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride : Cis. diammine bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) base (1 g) was suspended in water (15 ml), α -alanine (0.26 g) added and the mixture stirred first at room temperature and then on a steam bath. When evolution of ammonia had ceased the solution was cooled, neutralised with HCl (1:3), filtered and cooled in an ice bath for 2 hr. An orange yellow product was removed by filtration and the filtrate allowed to stand in a refrigerator overnight. Reddish violet crystals separated, which were recrystallised from hot 1:1 alcohol : water mixture.

[Found : N, 33.6 ; Cl, 15.4 ; Co, 12.7 ; H₂O, 7.7 per cent Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 33.8 ; Cl, 15.6 ; Co, 12.9 ; H₂O, 7.9 per cent].

d,l-α-alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) bromide : After neutralisation of the above reaction product with HCl, KBr was added in excess and cooled in a refrigerator overnight. The compound was recrystallised from hot water.

[Found : N, 28.5 ; Br, 29.0 ; Co, 11.1 ; H₂O, 6.6 ; per cent Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 28.3 ; Br, 29.3 ; Co, 10.8 ; H₂O, 6.6 per cent].

d,l-α-alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) iodide : To the above neutralised solution KI was added to precipitate reddish violet crystals which were purified twice from hot water.

[Found : N, 24.5 ; I, 40.5 ; Co, 9.6 ; H₂O, 2.6 per cent Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 24.8 ; I, 40.9 ; Co, 9.5 ; H₂O, 2.6 per cent].

The following two compounds were obtained by procedures similar to those for *d,l* α -alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) bromide and iodide salts.

β-alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) bromide : [Found : N, 28.9 ; Br, 29.5 ; Co, 10.6 ; H₂O, 5.5 ; per cent Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{ alan})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 28.7 ; Br, 29.8 ; Co, 11.0 ; H₂O, 5.5 per cent].

β-alaninato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) iodide : [Found : N, 24.9 ; I, 42.3 ; Co, 9.5 ; per cent Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-alan})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_2$ - N, 25.6 ; I, 42.1 ; Co, 9.8 per cent].

The following two compounds were prepared by procedures for *a*-histidinate bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) salts.

l-leucinato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride : Reddish violet needles, recrystallised from 1:1 alcohol : water mixture.

[Found : N, 29.6 ; Cl, 13.7 ; Co, 11.3 ; H₂O, 9.8 per cent ; Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{leuc})(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 29.8 ; Cl, 13.8 ; Co, 11.4 ; H₂O, 10.5 per cent].

l-leucinato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) bromide : Reddish violet needless, recrystallised from hot water.

[Found : N, 26.8 ; Br, 27.1 ; Co, 9.8 ; H₂O, 6.5 per cent ; Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{leuc})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 26.2 ; Br, 27.2 ; Co, 10.0 ; H₂O, 6.2 per cent].

For the following two compounds the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight when the mixed complex along with some yellow crystals separated, which were then fractionally crystallised as given below.

d,l-valinato bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride : Red violet crystals purified from 1:1 alcohol water mixture.

[Found : N, 28.9 ; Cl, 13.3 ; Co, 11.1 ; H₂O, 14.7 per cent ; Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{val})(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - N, 29.1 ; Cl, 13.4 ; Co, 11.1 ; H₂O, 15.3 per cent].

d,l-valinato bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) iodide : Red violet crystals purified from hot water.

[Found : N, 21.5 ; I, 36.3 ; Co, 8.6 ; H₂O, 10.3 per cent Calc ; for [Co(val) (BigH)₂]₂I₂·4H₂O - N, 21.9 ; I, 36.1 ; Co, 8.4 ; H₂O, 10.2 per cent].

Chromatography : Filter paper chromatography in aqueous KCl (0.2M) developer produces single spots indicating their identity as single species rather than a mixture of two homochelates. The R_f values are included in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE, EQUIVALENT WEIGHT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE MIXED CHELATES

Complex	Colour	R _f values in 0.2M KCl	Molar conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹ at 25°)	Equivalent weight		Electronic spectra	
				Found	Reqd.	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} (kK)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g} (kK)
[Co(hist) (BigH) ₂]Br ₂ ·H ₂ O	Orange red		218	339	344		
[Co(hist) (BigH) ₂] I ₂ ·H ₂ O	Orange red	.75		292	297	21.1	—
[Co(α-alan) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reddish violet	.80		228	228	20.41	27.78
[Co(α-alan) (BigH) ₂] I ₂ ·H ₂ O	Reddish violet		238	304	307	20.41	27.78
[Co(β-alan) (BigH) ₂] Br ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	Reddish violet	.80		267	268	20.41	—
[Co(β-alan) (BigH) ₂] I ₂	Reddish violet		264	306	302	20.41	
[Co(leuc) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Reddish violet	.80	203	261	258	20.41	27.78
[Co(leuc) (BigH) ₂] Br ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reddish violet			290	293		
[Co(val) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ ·4.5H ₂ O	Red violet	.81		260	264	20.41	27.78
[Co(val) (BigH) ₂] I ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Reddish violet		225	344	351		

Paper chromatography (ascending technique) of the complexes was done by using aqueous KCl (0.2M) as developer and sodium sulphide as spraying reagent. Equivalent weights were determined with the aid of H⁺ form cation exchanger (IR-120) column. An aqueous solution of the complex salt was run through the column and the effluent acid was titrated with a standard alkali solution. Cobalt was estimated as CoSO₄ and nitrogen by combustion method.

Results and Discussion

The mixed chelates were obtained by the action of histidine or the other amino acids on cis-diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) base. Several crystallisations from hot water or from 1 : 1 alcohol : water furnished analytically pure samples. The compounds are quite crystalline, look homogeneous single species under the microscope and are reasonably stable in aqueous solution. They have been characterised via elemental analysis, conductance, equivalent weight, chromatography, infrared and electronic spectra.

Conductance : The molar conductances (Table 1) in aqueous solutions at 25° are 210-265 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹, which are within the range of bivalent electrolytes⁹.

Equivalent weights : These values (Table 1) are also consistent with the elemental analysis and conductance data.

Electronic Spectra : Co(III) complexes commonly exhibit¹⁰ two spin allowed, Laporte forbidden transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g}. These transitions for our complexes are shown in Table 1. In orange-red coloured [Co(hist)(BigH)₂]I₂ only the ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition is observed. This transition is at a significantly higher energy (21.05 kK) compared to the transitions at about 20.4 kK for the red-violet coloured amino acid mixed chelates. Red-violet glycinate bis(biguanide) cobalt (III)¹¹ also absorbs at 20.4 kK. The ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition for the histidine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) is comparable to transitions in cobalt (III) complexes with [CoN₆] chromophores, for example, [Co(en) (BigH)₂]³⁺, 20.9 kK¹¹ ; [Co(dipy) (BigH)₂]³⁺, 21.4 kK¹² ; [Co(o-phen) (BigH)₂]³⁺, 21.3 kK¹² ; [Co(o-phen) (en)₂]³⁺, 21.5 kK¹³ and [Co(BigH)₃]³⁺, 21.1 kK¹⁴. It thus appears that histidine ion behaves as an NN bidentate donor in this mixed chelate using the imidazole and the NH₂ nitrogens for linking to cobalt (III). The higher energy transition ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} is presumably covered¹⁵ under the charge transfer transition arising out of an interaction between cobalt (III) and the imidazole moiety.

IR Spectra : The -C=N- stretch of biguanide being very much in the range of antisymmetrical car-

boxyl stretching region¹⁶ it frustrated attempts to demonstrate whether carboxyl group is free or not. Attempts to protonate COO^- by HCl to produce $[\text{Co}(\text{hist H})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ led to decomposition of the complex.

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Ionic Activity Products of $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in Acid Soils. Part II. Consecutive Leachings of Soils with and without Adding Phosphate in Neutral Salt Solutions

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THE constancy of pKsp values of $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ & $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been reported before on acid soils treated with KCL, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and CaCl_2 solutions of ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.04, the extractions being done on soils which were not P-treated. In the present paper three soils have been chosen in

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the pH range 4 to 6 extracted four times consecutively with 0.02M KCl (a) with out P-treatment and (b) with P-treatment, using prepared AIP, FeP and a mixture of (AIP+FeP). The phosphates were prepared according to the method of Gasser and Bloomfield², and had the compositions :

Aluminium Phosphate : $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ Compound formed.
= 1 : 1.9 $\text{Al}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$

Iron phosphate : $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ Compound formed is a mixture of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$
= 1 : 2.5

Details about the soil samples used are given in Table 1. Soils C-1 and C-2 were from Cinchona plantation and J-1 from wheat Cultivation.

TABLE I

Soil no.	pH.	Locality	Family	Depth of Sampling.	Colour	Total P Content	Organic Carbon
C-1	4.70	Mun-song	Hilly forest soil	0"-9"	Brownish black	7/100 29,700	1.43
C-2	5.77	Labdh	"	"	"	10,000	1.60
J-1	5.90	Jabal-pore	Sandy	"	Yellowish brown	12,500	0.28

Each soil was subjected to the following treatment.

- 1.0 g of soil + 500 ml of 0.02 M KCl solution
- 5.0 " " + 500 " " " " " "
- 5.0 " " + 0.5 g Fep. + 500 ml of 0.02 M KCl solution
- 5.0 " " + 0.5 " AIP + " " " "
- 5.0 " " + (0.25 " AIP + 0.25 " Fep) + " "

So that there were altogether 15 sets for the three soils. The mixtures were taken in separate bottles into which 1 ml of chloroform was added to prevent fungus growth. The bottles were shaken end-to-end for 2-3 hr a day during 10 days. At the completion of this period the pH of the soil suspension was measured using a Cambridge pH meter, and iron, aluminium and phosphate contents were determined in the filtrates.

After completion of the first extract 500 ml. of fresh 0.02M KCL was added to each bottle, any soil adhering to the filter paper being washed back to this bottle with the solution. This procedure was repeated four times with all the soils allowing equilibrium to attain each time. The pKsp values of $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were computed on each leaching according to the procedure described in the earlier paper. Ref of this Journal the results are shown in Table 2.

Results and Discussions

(i) Change in pH : values of soil suspensions were greatly influenced by the soil : solution ratio, an increase in the ratio from 1.0 g. to 5.0 g. soil leading to a lowering of pH in each case. This effect was more pronounced in the Cinchona soils (C-1, C-2) but less